

Biogas produced from biodegradable Waste

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ABSTRACT

Last year as a part of sustainable lab at the Roskilde Festival, our team investigated the potential for producing biogas from discarded food waste at the festival as a sustainable energy source. The subject of the 2011 Roskilde festival was poverty in Africa; the slogan was if it can be done at the Roskilde festival it can be done in Africa. With that in mind our team wanted to proof biogas could be produced under very low tech conditions from food waste, this is a prerequisite for implementing the technology in remote places in Africa where a sustainable heat and electricity is mostly needed.

Our investigation was showed that the festival discards a proximally 13 tons of biodegradable waste each year and the cost of waste management is high both economically and environmentally for the festival, most types of waste could successfully be converted to energy though biogas technology, in Africa the amount of biodegradable waste could provide a sustainable energy source at remote locations.

This year we propose a follow up investigation on a larger scale, we want to figure out what challenges there is both practically and economical in order to implement biogas production as a sustainable alternative to waste. We will do this by implementing biogas production from biodegradable waste at the Roskilde festival in cooperation with DTU Environment and DTU Risø